

FAMILY, KINSHIP RELATIONS AND THEIR LEGAL ANALYSIS AND REGULATION IN LAW.

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Annotation: This article discusses views on the family in the world and their comparison with the family in our country, as well as kinship relations and their legal basis.

Keywords: Person, family, law, Japan, Civil Code, civil law, husband, wife, legal relationship, Great Britain, family institution, concept, government decision, decree, Constitution, marriage, national tradition, values, Eastern thought, legislation, Family Code, kinship, family tree, direct family tree, side family tree, ancestor.

A person is born, grows up surrounded by a family, matures, and becomes an integral part of the life of the family he first grew up with, and later he built. In general, the family is one of the valuable blessings that can accompany a person during times of difficult decisions, overcome difficulties, and at the same time during happy times.

The concept of "family" is viewed differently in different parts of the world. In particular, according to Article 10 of the Civil Code, which is considered the main code of civil law in Japan, the family is a method of regulating certain legal relations between husband and wife, parents and children, as well as husband or wife and indirectly defining its scope¹. In Great Britain, the family is considered as a primary social group consisting of parents and their descendants, whose main task is to provide for its members².

The family is considered sacred in our country, and large-scale reforms are being carried out in order to comprehensively develop this institution, increase its strength, and educate young people in the spirit of family love. In order to create the legal basis of these reforms and give them a legal tone, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approving the concept of strengthening the institution of the family in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted³. "On measures to further support and bring the system of work with

¹ <https://www.mofa.go.jp> website of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan

² <https://culturalatlas.sbs.com.au>

³ National database of legal documents, PD-3808 dated 27.06.2018

family and women to a new level" was signed⁴ and government decisions were approved to ensure their implementation.

According to Article 76 of the newly revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the family is the main link of society and is under the protection of society and the state. Marriage is based on the traditional family values of the people of Uzbekistan, voluntary consent and equal rights of the spouses. The state creates social, economic, legal and other conditions for the full development of the family. In fact, the norms of family and kinship relations in our country are formed in harmony with the values, national traditions, oriental thinking and modern lifestyle trends that have been formed in the Uzbek people for many years. So, what is kinship? Kinship is a concept that expresses socio-historical blood relations between people and mutual spiritual closeness⁵. Kinship groups are social units, membership in which requires adherence to specific rules and control over the activities of each group member, and the number of kinship term systems is limited, with four of these systems for the parent generation and six systems for each generation, including siblings. includes brothers, sisters and uncles⁶. In contrast, our local people describe kinship based on the following genealogy. These are:

- 1) parents,
- 2) child,
- 3) grandson,
- 4) great-grandson(called evara),
- 5) great-grandson(called chevara),
- 6) nobora,
- 7) dubora and subsequent generations are called strangers.

In fact, in our legislation, kinship issues are given a wide place and explained in an understandable way. In particular, persons descended from one common third person (ancestor) are relatives. The closeness of kinship between two persons according to the correct genealogy is determined by the degree of kinship, that is, the number of births. In this case, children are considered to be the first relative in the correct family tree in relation to their parents, the grandchild is the second relative to their grandfather, grandmother, the great-grandchild is the third relative to their great-grandfather, great-grandmother, and so on. Also, brothers, sisters and their children, parents' brothers and sisters

⁴ <https://lex.uz> 18.02.2020. PD-5938

⁵ <http://forum.oyina.uz>

⁶ K.F. Kottak. Textbook "Cultural Anthropology".

and their children, grandparents' brothers and sisters and their children and the like by sideline are relatives and so on. It follows that relatives on the right family tree are closer than relatives on the side family tree. When determining the distance of kinship between two persons, the number of degrees or the number of descendants from one of these persons, without taking into account the person himself, is taken into account. It is carried towards the common person (ancestor) and from him to the descendants - towards the other one of them. Birth brothers and sisters are on the second level of kinship, uncles and aunts are on the third level of kinship with their nieces and nephews, and uncles, cousins, aunts and uncles are on the fourth level of kinship⁷. Kinship, in turn, has two forms:

1. Unmixed kinship.
2. Mixed kinship.

In this case, according to the norms of the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, brothers and sisters can be unmixed and mixed relatives. If brothers and sisters come from the same parents, the father is not mixed, the father is the same mother, or vice versa, the mother is the same father, then it is considered a mixed relative. In unmixed kinship, brothers and sisters are born, and in mixed kinship, brothers and sisters are considered step-brothers. Therefore, it can be said that the children of the spouses from previous marriages are not considered relatives.

In short, in the legal system of our country, the attention to the institution of family and kinship relations is considered high in comparison with international legislation, and any reforms implemented in this field do not lose their relevance, in which the legal norms and legislative documents, which are the basis of reforms, are historically It is not an exaggeration to say that it is being accepted in the spirit of the emerging nationality.

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1. National database of legal documents, PD-3808 dated 27.06.2018
2. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 76.
3. K.F. Kottak. Textbook "Cultural Anthropology".
4. Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 57
5. <https://www.mofa.go.jp> website of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan
6. <https://culturalatlas.sbs.com.au>

⁷ Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 57

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